

Traces of Inorganic Explosives in the Sewer System - A Review

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Abstract

This review focuses on the presence and the expected concentration of ions related to inorganic explosives in wastewater/sewage. The ionic composition of waste water treatment plant (WWTP) influent has been frequently reported, but has been limited to a few inorganic anions and cations. Identified concentrations of ions in wastewater are 5 - 200 mg/L for major ions, 0.1 - 217 µg/L for heavy metal ions and 0.014 -1.6 mg/L for some also explosive related anions. The discussed methods to monitor wastewater/sewage over an extended period of time look promising, but need to overcome pre-treatment and sampling issues (filtration, dilution) and also the selectivity and sensitivity needs to be improved. The most promising method is based on sequential injection capillary electrophoresis coupled with capacitive-coupled contactless conductivity detection (SI-CE-C⁴D) and is capable of simultaneous detection of cations and anions with an LOD of 0.005 to 0.061 mg/L, and more importantly portable and automatable. The data provided for this work shows that the levels for the ions of interest cover a broad range, from values under the limit of quantification (<LOQ) up to 200 mg/L for chloride. These findings will also contribute valid information to the selection of ions for monitoring purposes and therefore be a possible application for the evaluation of the New Year's Eve Effect (NYEE) in wastewater/sewage.

Keywords Inorganic Explosive, Wastewater, Sewage, New Year's Eve Effect, Influences

Introduction

Monitoring the composition of wastewater is common practice in every wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). A qualitative and quantitative detection of contaminants such as cleaning products, fertilizers, pharmaceuticals and legal/illegal drugs are crucial for the later removal process. The terms 'wastewater' and 'sewage' are commonly used as synonyms to describe the complex matrix of water containing several kinds of pollutants such as organic matter, inorganic compounds/metals, organisms, pathogens and nutrients. Wastewater is affected by human behaviour (municipal, industrial) and sewage is subset of wastewater. Anything that can be flushed down a toilet, a drain, or a sewer will be a potential pollutant of sewage, which can affect the composition of wastewater, which in turn can have an impact on the environment. Sewage epidemiology is the idea that temporal changes in the composition of wastewater and sewage can be directly related to human behaviour and the first practical approach using cocaine as a model drug has been performed in 2005 in Italy.^{1,2} Since 2008³ the analysis of metabolites of illicit drugs in wastewater have been widely investigated firstly throughout multiple studies from different cities in Europe e.g. Paris⁴, Zagreb⁵ and Brussels⁶. Secondly to survey spatial differences and temporal changes in an even larger population Thomas et al. and Ort C. et al. published the first Europe-wide studies of illicit drug consumption estimation through municipal wastewater and sewage analysis.^{7,8} The European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA) thereto

an annual report about the analysis of wastewater to explore illegal drug taking habits of inhabitants from different European cities. In the 2018 report, wastewater of approx. 43 million people was analysed for traces of amphetamine, cocaine, ecstasy and methamphetamine including 60 European cities.⁹ These studies provide a large amount of data that shows spatial differences, temporal changes (week, weekend) and short- and long term trends (yearly ranking of cities) in drug taking habits of a huge population. The data and results are yearly updated online, on an interactive platform (<http://www.emcdda.europa.eu/topics/pods/waste-water-analysis>). Studies mentioned such as the estimation of consumption of illicit drugs and traces of organic explosive in wastewater¹⁰⁻¹² show clearly that human behaviour and lifestyle can lead to composition changes of wastewater.

The EU-funded project called EMPHASIS (Explosive Material Production Hidden Agile Search and Intelligence System) carried out by nine project partners and coordinated by the Swedish Defence Research Agency (FOI) from late 2011 till early 2015, focused on the development of techniques that would be able to monitor and detect explosive related vapours in the air, traces on surfaces and in water, to being able to locate illicit bomb factories in urban areas.¹³ Two EMPHASIS project outcomes in regards to the matrix of wastewater are discussed in this review. The (NYEE) has been described as the increase of the concentration of several chemical compounds related to explosives in the environment after celebrations (New Year's Eve, Chinese New Year, San Juan), including the use of fireworks. When it comes to New Year's Eve (NYE) and the celebration with fireworks, the Dutch have been described as a nation of secret pyro technicians. Buying fireworks is only allowed on December 29, 30 and 31 and further regulations limit down the use to an eight hour timeframe from the 31st Dec - 6pm to 1st Jan - 2am (§ 3 Article 2.3.2, Vuurwerkbesluit¹⁴). Besides the arrests and injuries related to fireworks the police reported a 9% increase in the violence against emergency services. Those institutions have been calling for broader restrictions or bans on consumer fireworks. In contrast for the NYE 2018/2019 the Dutch spend around 70 Mill. Euro on legal fireworks, 3% more than last year (31st Dec 2019, NU.nl¹⁵), and not to forget the unknown cases of illegally obtained fireworks through smuggling and online shopping. We know from studies that indeed big events such as New Year's Eve, Chinese New Year and San Juan lead to concentration changes of target ions in samples collected from surfaces during celebrations¹⁶, due to the enormous release of legal fireworks in a short period of time. Why not trying to determine the impact on the environment in the sewer system by measuring the ions related to explosives in wastewater/sewage, what presumably can help intelligence and police forces to narrow down the search area for illegal manufacturing sites of improvised explosive devices (IEDs) or fireworks?

Firstly we need to know if there are ions of interest present and what are expected concentrations. Secondly possible interferences (e.g. temperature, pH, weather), spatial differences (urban, suburban) and temporal changes (seasonal, celebrations) of those ions in the matrix wastewater/sewage have to be assessed. Therefore, the aim of this work is to determine the presence and concentration ranges in which ions of interest are present and to which extend are significant changes in the concentration of targeted ions in wastewater/sewage. Finally the New Year's Eve Effect (NYEE) would be a good application to study the influences and changes on the matrix wastewater during celebrations with fireworks, with respect to ion composition, separation and detection technique, which in turn presumably can detect illegal manufacturing sites of explosives/fireworks through sewage analysis.

Review of Separation Methods and Sensors

The detection of organic ions of explosives in wastewater or sewage are widely based on various forms of liquid-chromatography (LC) as well as (ultra) high performance liquid-chromatography ((U)HPLC) and (tandem-)mass spectrometry [(MS)/MS], which are highly sensitive, well established and versatile methods.¹⁰⁻¹² By contrast the approach of monitoring and evaluating inorganic ions related to explosives in wastewater/sewage is still in its infancy. The ideal method should fulfil the following criteria for the determination of the concentration of target ions (Table 1, 2): acceptable analysis time; simple/no sample pre-treatment; required selectivity and sensitivity, low cost single analysis and ideally in-situ real-time detection. Since, up to date as far as we know, there are no comprehensive methods, the best methodology analysing this matrix and those ions are shown in Table 1 and discussed in this review.

Ion chromatography (IC) methods are routinely used applications in wastewater laboratories and a widely accepted reference method for ion analysis in water and wastewater.¹⁷ Capillary electrophoresis (CE) was first introduced as a complementary method for IC in 1992.¹⁸ After the first appearance in the early 1990 CE became a reliable separation method and well established technique for detecting inorganic ions of explosive residues^{18,19}, although not fully comparable to other techniques in the field (HPLC, GC). In comparison to IC, CE is overall less expensive, needs less background electrolyte (BGE), and has high flexibility and tolerance towards great variations in sample matrices.²⁰ The broad range of literature shows that CE has been intensively used for the identification of explosive related ions in soil and residue extracts from intact (pre-blast residues) or detonated IEDs (post-blast residues).²¹⁻²⁸ CE can also be highly sensitive in separation of explosive related ions and is able to separate organic anions like acetate, benzoate^{22,23}, oxalate, formate, methylamine²⁹ and inorganic anions related to explosives. Studies have been carried out with model solutions like artificial wastewater but seldom with real wastewater samples. Sampling challenges for the future of automated real-time monitoring of explosive related ions in wastewater/sewage are the necessity of sample pre-treatment including the filtration of solid material and dissolved organic matter (DOM), and the dilution of the sample up to 20-fold³⁰ before analysis.

Table 1: Different detection methods for ion chromatography and capillary electrophoreses with regards to the analysis of explosive related ions in different aqueous matrices.

Technique	Cations	Anions	W	N	S	LOD (mg/L)	*
(novel APS) ICP-MS	Cd ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺			✓		0.00296 - 0.01750	31
IC-ICP-MS	Cd ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺			✓		0.0001 - 0.0005	32
IC-ICP-MS		ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , BrO ₃ ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻ , IO ₃ ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻		✓		0.0001 - 0.5	32
IC-ESI-SQ-MS	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺			✓		0.0002 - 0.00366	32
IC-ESI-TQ-MS		ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , BrO ₃ ⁻ , IO ₃ ⁻		✓		0.000015 - 0.001	32

IC-conductivity detection	K ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , CH ₃ NH ₃ ⁺ , CH ₃ CH ₂ NH ₃ ⁺	ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , BrO ₃ ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , CNO ⁻ , SCN ⁻ , CrO ₄ ²⁻ , acetate, benzoate, formate	✓	0.002 - 0.0274 anions 0.013 - 0.115 cations	33
IC-conductivity detection		Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , CN ⁻ as CNO ⁻	✓	0.0027 - 0.0088	34
IEC/CEC-conductivity detection	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Cl ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻	✓ ✓	0.7 - 0.8 μM anions 1.6 - 2.9 μM cations 0.11 - 0.13 μM phosphate	35
CZE- and ITP-CZE-conductivity detection	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺		✓	0.02 - 0.04	30
(portable) CE-C ⁴ D	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , CH ₃ NH ₃ ⁺ , CH ₃ CH ₂ NH ₃ ⁺	ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , CNO ⁻ , SCN ⁻ , acetate, benzoate	✓	0.027 - 0.240 anions 0.031 - 0.240 cations	23
CE-C ⁴ D		ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , N ₃ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , SCN ⁻	✓	0.018 - 0.079	24
(single) SI-CE-C ⁴ D	NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻	✓	0.03 - 0.11	36
(dual) SI-CE-C ⁴ D	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻	✓ ✓	0.005 - 0.061	37
CE-UV (LED)	K ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , CH ₃ NH ₃ ⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , CH ₃ CH ₂ NH ₃ ⁺	ClO ₄ ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , PO ₃ ⁴⁻ , CNO ⁻ , SCN ⁻ , acetate, benzoate	✓	0.11 - 2.30 cations 0.24 - 1.15 anions	22

Literature (*), Limit of detection (LOD), active-passive sampling (APS), sewage/model solution/artificial wastewater (W), natural/surface water like drinking, tap, sea, lake, river (N), soil or residues extracts (S).

IC coupled with various mass spectrometry applications (e.g. ICP-MS, ESI-MS) is still the most sensitive method for determining ions in water, it is especially selective for cations and can reach a sensitivity from a LOD of μg/L to sub-μg/L.³² However this method will be not suitable for the simultaneous analysis of both ion species. IC coupled with (non-)suppressed conductivity detection shows similar LOD (sub-mg/L) in comparison with CE coupled with capacitively-coupled contactless conductivity detection (CE-C⁴D). A method that has been developed in 2015 for a better separation of common anions from cyanide in natural and seawaters reached a LOD of μg/L.³⁴ The method was developed overcome the high concentration of chloride in seawater and the interference of CN⁻ and NO₂⁻ due to similar retention times. After cyanide-cyanate conversion the method can tolerate a Cl⁻/CN⁻ ratio of 3000, this could be useful tool to consider for the analysis of municipal and urban wastewaters. Because wastewater contains a high level of chloride and low levels of nitrite see e.g. in Table 5, and cyanate is one of the inorganic explosive related anions (Table 1). P. Kuban and P.C. Hauser reviewed in 2018 the development of C⁴D, with the conclusion that C⁴D has been proven to be an efficient technique for detection of charged inorganic, organic and biochemical analytes.³⁸ The most promising method towards simultaneous

analysis of anions and cations in wastewater seems to be CE coupled with C⁴D. These matrices analysed with CE in previous studies had been mostly focused on extraction of explosive residues or soil samples for identification of anions with C⁴D^{23,24}, indirect UV-Vis^{26,27} or multiple light emitting diode (LEDs)²² to detect both ionic species. The limit of detection for C⁴D was sub-mg/L, for LED the LOD was sub-mg/L to mg/L. Kuban et al. proposed a new fully portable CE-C⁴D suitable for water analysis and other environmental samples in 2007 including tests in a remote area in Tasmania to reach low LOD.³⁹ However to reach such low levels of detection (10 ppb for NO₂⁻ and NH₄⁺) the device was designed to work with low background noise, what makes the method useful for monitoring natural waters but not wastewaters. In 2010, Mai et al. presented a SI-CE-C⁴D (SI = sequential injection) system especially designed for monitoring fully automated over several days on-site the concentrations of inorganic anions and cations in a creek.⁴⁰ A promising method was published in 2013, a novel method for simultaneous and rapid separation of anions and cations from a single sample using dual-capillary sequential injection-capillary electrophoresis ((dual)SI-CE-C⁴D).³⁷ Gaudry et al. achieved the simultaneous separation and detection of 23 inorganic and organic anions within 3 min and were able to analyse water over period of 50 h with high reproducibility, temporal stability and fully automated (Figure 1). The inorganic ions in this study were selected with priority on water quality analysis, but more importantly taking ions for explosive and common environmental background into account. Besides its good separation and high sensitivity, in this study the outcome for tap-water, process water of a zinc manufacturing plant and an ion model solution and did not experienced the difficulties of the matrix wastewater/sewage. The method of Gaudry et al. would be the closest to a comprehensive method which we need for the aim of the whole research. However for an ideal approach we need to overcome the weaknesses of this method what is the lack of studies in actual wastewater and selectivity.

Figure 1. Left: Separations of (a) standard analyte mixture plus internal standards, (b) process water from a zinc manufacturing plant and (c) 23 small ions. In all electropherograms, anion signals (black) are overlaid with corresponding cation signals (red). CE conditions for a–c: see original article. Analyte identities: (1) NH₄⁺, (2) K⁺, (3) Ca²⁺, (4) Na⁺, (5) Mg²⁺, (6) Cl⁻, (7) NO₃⁻, (8) SO₄²⁻, (9) ClO₄⁻, (10) ClO₃⁻, (11) F⁻, (12) PO₄³⁻, (13) CO₃²⁻, (14) CH₃SO₃⁻ [IS], (15) Li⁺ [IS], (16) (CrO₄)²⁻, (17) MoO₄²⁻, (18) C₃H₈SO₃⁻, (19) Mn²⁺, (20) Zn²⁺, (21) Sr²⁺, (22) Cd²⁺, (23) Cr³⁺, (24) Be²⁺, (25) Fe²⁺, and (*) unidentified ion. Right: (a) Reproducibility of corrected migration times of tap water analytes over a continuous 50 h period. (b) A representative electropherogram of the separation. Reprinted from Publication: Gaudry, A. J. *et al.* On-line simultaneous and rapid separation of anions and cations from a single sample using dual-capillary sequential injection-capillary electrophoresis. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **781**, 80–87 (2013), with permission from Elsevier.

Another promising method for detecting inorganic ions in wastewater is using different electrodes or sensors. In 2019 investigated single separation capillaries, C⁴D detection and a sequential injection manifold ((single)SI-CE-C⁴D) for automated on-line monitoring of wastewater.³⁶ The filtration problem was approached with a commercially available membrane module (pore size 0.2 μm). The experiment was focused on the simultaneous detection of nitrogen species, such as NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻, while continuous monitoring of wastewater, with a LOD of 0.03 - 0.11 mg/L and a high stability over several hours. Figure 2 shows not only the separation of the targeted ions for wastewater analysis, but also other interesting species related to explosives. This approach is a highly promising method for future research towards monitoring of inorganic explosive ions in sewage and sewage epidemiology, although a better sensitivity and selectivity would be required.

Figure 2. (a) Simultaneous separation of anions and cations in a wastewater sample; Capillary ID: 20 μm, effective length: 68 cm; Buffer solution: 100 mM His/100 mM MES/0.13 mM CTAB/1.5 mM 18-crown-6, pH 6; Voltage: +24 kV. (b) Stability investigation of peak areas of standard solution, during continuous wastewater monitoring. Reprinted from Publication: Fuiko, R., Saracevic, E., Koenka, I. J., Hauser, P. C. & Krampe, J. Capillary electrophoresis for continuous nitrogen quantification in wastewater treatment processes. *Talanta* **195**, 366–371 (2019), with permission from Elsevier.

In 2013 a sewage sensor system for the complex matrix of sewage water was proposed and investigated by Heil et al.⁴¹ The system developed and tested combined various ion-selective, reference and other electrodes, which creating extensive data sets, to be able to detect traces of suspicious materials in wastewater. While this approach shows a promising application to identify cations in artificial sewage it has not been sufficient for anions. Systems for real-time monitoring have been developed for drinking water measuring pH, turbidity, free chlorine, and temperature.⁴² The approach of using multiple electrodes for real-time wastewater monitoring to detect illegal waste discharge in the sewer system (pH, conductivity, chloride concentration) was proposed and tested by Hauser et al in 2019.⁴³ The selected parameters were not reasonable for differentiation of illegal waste and normal household chemicals. But more important the approach of Hauser et al. reveals limitations of real-time monitoring in sewage, such as natural downstream dilution up to 50-fold after 10 m and sensor/electrode clogging with solid material after longer exposure in sewage shown in Figure 3. Gallardo-Gonzalez et al. presented in 2019 a new generation of fully integrated passive microfluidic Lab-on-a-Chip (LOC) application for in-situ electrochemical real-time detection of ammonium in flowing water.⁴⁴ The robustness of the LOC had been tested under real conditions in a municipal sewage pipe in Berlin (flow rate 10-15 L/s, velocity of 0-0.8 m/s) and was functioning at least 15 min after exposure. The low-cost, easy-to-operate and miniaturized LOC, with a LOD of 40 μM and a response time of 10-12 s seems to be a promising approach for continuous monitoring. The design of the LOC made it possible to naturally create a water stream

through the microfluidic LOC while emerged in a laminar water flow (sewage pipe). Because there is no need of an external pump it reduces the power consumption to zero and is therefore an extremely helpful applications for difficult environments.⁴⁴ Another highly interesting approach towards detection of explosives traces in wastewater with electrochemical sensors was proposed and investigated in the work of Desmet et al. in 2017.⁴⁵ The electrochemical sensor system was trained to recognize chemical patterns of IEDs in multiple ‘real’ aqueous samples, such as surface water and drinking water, releasing an alarm by positive identification. The limitation was the artificially produced solution which mimicked wastewater. The scenarios tested in this approach gave in the majority of tests a correct prediction. The probabilities for the predictions reached 0-0.82% for non-identification and 93-100% for identification. Furthermore, the alarm system was not only successfully tested in the laboratory but also under ‘real’ conditions with additional target substances and other interfering species. The target compound are declared as B01, B08, and B15, which are explosive precursors used for manufacturing IEDs (no real names available due to security disclosure reasons and the security of the counter-explosive EU action). The system had one unclear classification and three false positives out of the 19 tests under ‘real’ conditions, by identifying B01 as a mix of B01+B08 and therefore raising a false alarm. Overall the sensor alarm system could be a promising approach towards an alarm system that could recognize not only the compounds itself but also patterns of chemicals used to build IEDs, which would add more evidential value to the analysis of explosives in wastewater from a forensic point of view. Further the implementation of a continuous monitoring strategy method opens up many possibilities to novel developments for fully automated control systems, what could be of high interest for police investigation and intelligence.

Figure 3: Clogging effect on electrodes after exposure in raw wastewater/sewage⁴³; Taylor & Francis is pleased to offer reuses of its content for a thesis or dissertation free of charge contingent on resubmission of permission request if work is published.

Review and Study of Wastewater Ion Composition from Literature and WWTP Database

In contradiction to the existing literature this review emphasis on the ‘natural’ presents of explosive related ions in the matrix of wastewater/sewage, establish a time-dependent, spatial background level of those ions and investigate possible influences and limitations. The main focus of this review is to determine presence and expected concentration of ions of interest. Therefore, the ionic composition of sewage/wastewater and IEDs will be discussed. Data from literature and statistical data from two WWTPs in the province of Girona (Spain) will also be assessed and discussed. The focus will be on the questions which ions are present, what are the expected concentrations and could we evaluate the influences and changes occurring, due to the extensive use of fireworks during celebrations (New Year’s Eve Effect), in the ionic composition sewage/wastewater?

Composition of Improvised Explosive Devices, Inorganic Explosives and Pyrotechnic

Most inorganic compounds containing salts of chlorate, perchlorate and nitrate are considered to be low order explosives. IEDs can be manufactured with both high and low order explosives, as well as legal/illegal pyrotechnic mixtures. In 2006 researchers analysed the composition of low explosives (pre and post-blast) of around 1000 case related residue samples with SEM-EDX.⁴⁶ Twenty-one possible compositions of improvised explosive mixtures were identified and grouped in four main categories: nitrate-, chlorate-, nitrate/chlorate- and permanganate-based explosive mixtures. Respectively, the first three composition types were present in ~94% of the investigated cases. Research towards the determination of the ionic composition of pre-blast residues as well as post-blast residues (PBRs) from explosive devices, like consumer firework^{16,27}, Molotov cocktail²⁶, AFNO⁴⁷ and other IEDs^{22,24,28,33,48-50}, with various capillary electrophoresis separation techniques emerged in recent years. Blanco et al. identified hereby beside the major contributors' chlorate, perchlorate and nitrate, also azide as a 'marker' to identify IEDs.

Table 2: Inorganic ion species of interest regarding inorganic explosives, pyrotechnic compositions and IEDs derived from those inorganic compositions.

Cations				Anions			
Sodium	Na ⁺	Copper	Cu ²⁺	Chlorate	ClO ₃ ⁻	Iodate	IO ₃ ⁻
Potassium	K ⁺	Strontium	Sr ²⁺	Chlorite	ClO ₂ ⁻	Sulfate	SO ₄ ²⁻
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	Manganese	Mn ²⁺	Chloride	Cl ⁻	Thiosulfate	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻
Caesium	Cs ⁺	Cadmium	Cd ²⁺	Perchlorate	ClO ₄ ⁻	Bromate	BrO ₃ ⁻
Magnesium	Mg ²⁺	Cobalt	Co ²⁺	Azide	N ₃ ⁻	Bromide	Br ⁻
Calcium	Ca ²⁺	Nickel	Ni ²⁺	Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻	Cyanate	OCN ⁻
Barium	Ba ²⁺	Iron	Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Nitrite	NO ₂ ⁻	Thiocyanate	SCN ⁻
Zinc	Zn ²⁺	Aluminium	Al ³⁺	Phosphate	PO ₄ ³⁻	Chromate	CrO ₄ ²⁻
Lead	Pb ²⁺	Arsenic	As ³⁺	Iodate	I ⁻	Fluoride	F ⁻
Chromium	Cr ³⁺						

A review about analytical techniques for intact explosive devices with focus on consumer fireworks showed diverse composition profiles, although the compounds potassium perchlorate/nitrate, aluminium and magnesium were particularly highlighted.⁵¹ The composition profile of illegal fireworks and IEDs are important when it comes to reconstruction and interpretation in forensic casework, in this case especially for the justifiable selection of inorganic ions suitable for monitoring in wastewater. Illegal fireworks or IEDs are not static in composition due to the fact that those devices are improvised manufactured items with legal and illegal components. The existing literature/reviews dealing with the identification of the composition of fireworks and IEDs, identified not only major contributors but also 'marker' ions such as perchlorate and azide, which are specific for some explosive devices, but hardly present in wastewater. This fact could make those 'marker' ions good candidates for a monitoring approach. Table 2 shows the inorganic ions related to IEDs, fireworks and their probable decomposition products and Table 3 shows the few organic ions related to IEDs.

Table 3: Organic ion species of interest regarding organic explosives, pyrotechnic compositions and IEDs derived from those organic compositions.

Cations		Anions	
Methyl ammonium			
Ethyl ammonium			
Urea			
Dicyandiamide			
		Terephthalate	

Composition of Wastewater/Sewage

Human activity produces wastewater and a substantial part of it will be discharged as sewage. The quantity/quality of wastewater from households depends strongly on the behaviour and lifestyle from the humans producing it - "Show me your wastewater and I will tell you who you are". The most popular inorganic (soluble) species found in wastewater are metals, ammonium, nitrite, nitrate, and *ortho*-phosphate, sulfate and chloride. Measurements like pH, conductivity and alkalinity are routine water chemistry analytic. What affects the wastewater composition the most is the design of the sewer system, which is in most developed countries separated from the wastewater system (exceptions in urban areas).⁵² Therefore, wastewater and sewage are complex mixtures of several inorganic and organic pollutants. Knowledge about the ion composition of 'normal' wastewater/sewage or average values, will be fundamental for the realisation of a spatial baseline ("background"). The concentration of ions in municipal wastewater/sewage are influenced by the contribution of industrial wastewater and the dilution due to changes in consumption (inhabitants) and infiltration (storm water). The concentration of nitrogen (N_{total}) and phosphorus (P_{total}) in wastewater has an influence on the treatment that will follow, therefore the monitoring of those

soluble nutrients are normal practice. Table 4 shows the expected concentrations for nitrogen and phosphorus in wastewater (total influent) and the concentrations of the inorganic ions ammonium, nitrate, nitrite and *ortho*-phosphate which are also related to explosives. The data shows that nitrate/nitrite are hardly present in wastewater (sub-mg level) but ammonia/ammonium can be found in concentrations from 20 to 75 mg/L and *ortho*-phosphate from 3 to 15 mg/L.

Table 4: Concentration range of typically monitored nutrients of interest related to explosives in raw municipal wastewater (mg/L).

Parameter		(a) ⁵²	(b) ⁵³	(c) ⁴³	(d) ⁵⁴
N _{total}	Org. N + inorg. N	30 - 100	35 - 60	67 - 93	40 - 85
Nitrate + Nitrite N	NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻	0.1 - 0.5	~ 0	N/A	N/A
Ammonia N	NH ₃ , NH ₄ ⁺	20 - 75	20 - 35	40 - 65	N/A
P _{total}	Org. P + <i>ortho</i> -P	6 - 25	4 - 15	9 - 13	6 - 12
<i>ortho</i> -Phosphate P	PO ₄ ³⁻	4 - 15	3 - 9	N/A	N/A

N/A = not reported.

Metal ions are typically present in soil but can also be found in wastewater (Table 5). Some of those ions are existential to plants and animals (K⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe^{2/3+}) in small quantities, others are toxic and deadly if they exceed threshold concentrations (Ni²⁺, Hg₂²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cr³⁺, Cd²⁺). Table 4 shows concentrations for selected metal ions that can be found in municipal wastewater influent. The first column (R) shows a range were the lower value is related to high water consumption/infiltration and is therefore more diluted and the high value related to low water consumption/infiltration and is therefore less diluted.⁵² The next three columns show reported averages of metal concentrations in the Netherlands (NL) of one unspecified WWTP⁵⁵, of 4 different WWTPs (Amersfoort, Kralingseveer, Nieuwgraaf, Venlo)⁵⁶ and of all WWTPs of the Netherlands (CLO data 2015). The majority of the reported averages falls in or under the reported range.⁵² The concentrations of metal ions can spatial and temporal fluctuate even throughout the Netherlands (Table 5).

Table 5: Concentrations of metals in (influent) wastewater.

Parameter		R ⁵²	NL 2016 ⁵⁵	NL 2018 ⁵⁶	NL 2015*
		(µg/L)	(µg/L)	(µg/L)	(µg/L)
Mercury	Hg ₂ ²⁺	1 - 3	0.1	0.12	0.1
Cadmium	Cd ²⁺	1 - 4	2.7	0.24	0.3
Arsenic	As ³⁺	N/A	3.7	2.4	3.7
Chromium	Cr ³⁺	10 - 40	5.2	18	9
Nickel	Ni ²⁺	10 - 40	5.5	28.4	10
Lead	Pb ²⁺	25 - 80	10.5	13	18
Copper	Cu ²⁺	30 - 100	62.8	92	74
Zinc	Zn ²⁺	100 - 300	225	215	217

*Influent average in the Netherlands (NL) based on CLO data (2015), N/A = not reported, R = range reported.

New Year's Eve Effect in Wastewater

Once we have established a background level for ions of interest and overcome analytical obstacles the possible applications are the detection of illegal manufacturing sites, terrorist headquarters and the evaluation of the New Year's Eve Effect (NYEE) in wastewater. The investigation if the New Year's Eve Effect⁵⁷ could be observable in wastewater I analysed data from two different WWTPs in Spain (Girona and Quart). The data examined in this work was kindly provided by Dr. Pablo Gago-Ferrero and his colleagues from the Catalan Institute for Water Research (ICRA) in Girona, Spain. The increase of the concentrations of ions related to fireworks in wastewater should therefore be an ideal indicator to see which ions are increasing, due to the extensive use of fireworks during that special day. Therefore the New Year's Eve Effect could be a reasonable explanation for the changes of some ions in wastewater related to the use of explosives/fireworks. Figure 4 plots data from the WWTP Quart in Spain were samples were taken on two occasions in September and December, plus once after NYE on the 8th of January 2019 (Table 6).

Table 6: Anion and cation concentrations (mg/L) determined in wastewater from the WWTP of Quart, a small city in the north of Spain with 3750 inhabitants as of 2017.

Day	Chloride	Sodium	Ammonium	Calcium	Potassium	Phosphate	Magnesium
06 Sep	168.625	145.560	66.446	62.910	27.920	21.294	16.722
15 Sep	153.525	129.428	77.144	57.287	24.301	3.467	13.725
02 Dec	115.667	88.850	74.599	73.096	22.440	7.667	14.943
12 Dec	100.283	64.627	38.024	43.542	13.512	4.564	9.239
08 Jan	204.818	142.569	115.922	78.731	49.698	40.194	23.743
	Sulfate	Chlorite	Chlorate	Nitrite	Nitrate	Fluoride	Bromide
06 Sep	12.995	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.405	1.434
15 Sep	7.302	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.000	<LOQ	0.155	1.586
02 Dec	17.388	0.000	0.000	0.031	0.000	0.100	0.000
12 Dec	22.846	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.100	0.000
08 Jan	15.025	0.000	0.014	0.026	0.036	0.148	0.000

<LOQ = under limit of quantification, Sep = September, Dec = December, Jan = January.

The data included values of the composition of wastewater influent before and after New Year's Eve compared to the middle of the year, with focus on ions related to fireworks/explosives. Assuming that approx. 3750 inhabitants celebrated NYE and the "Festival of the three Magic Kings" on 6th of January with fireworks, the concentration of sulfate in wastewater after the celebrations compared to before increased 100%, that for sodium and chloride 200%, ammonium and magnesium 300%, potassium 400% and most significant increase of around 900% for *ortho*-phosphate. All measured cations and chloride and phosphate are the highest 9 days after NYE (8th of January) compared to 19 days (12th of December) before, were it was the lowest form all data points. Those changes could be closely related to NYE, because the ions identified in fireworks are also highly elevated in the wastewater and could therefore be a great evaluation tool for the New Year's Eve Effect, but the data is not yet enough to determine a trend or even draw any valid conclusion. More data is needed to identify first the ions that are in this data under the LOQ, so we can conclude on which levels of concentration we actually have to measure and as a result how sensitive our instruments have to be in the future. However there are indications and already some information in this data we can use to determine the next steps towards a method development and experiment planning, to study this issue.

We know that the regularly monitored ions can change in concentration levels of 5-200 mg/L during the year. The majority of determined anions (see Figure 4, right diagram) are in levels of 0.014-1.6 mg/L and chlorate, chlorite, nitrite and nitrate are in 1 to 2 data points under LOQ. Influences like dilution from rain can be excluded since it did not rain in Girona, Spain from the 1st to the 8th of January.⁵⁸ This observation leads to the assumption that those ion concentrations are only high enough for the detection method used, because of their already higher availability in the environment (seasons, human activity) or due to the extensive use of fireworks (NYE), both are valid assumptions that needs to be proven with more sensitive and continuous measurement applications. The data indicates decreasing concentrations for fluoride and bromide after the beginning of September, with bromide as an extreme example being present in September but not in December/January.

Figure 4: Plot of the composition of wastewater from the WWTP of Quart at different dates of the year, the left diagram shows the plot enhanced for the ions from chlorite to bromide, Sep = September, Dec = December, Jan = January.

More empirical data from more narrow time intervals or continuous statistical data (daily, hourly) needs to be obtained to be able to determine a significant trend that leads to the conclusion that the NYEE could indeed be validated through concentration changes of ions in wastewater. Another dataset given by the same contact contains more data points (Table 7) and the plot of the data in Figure 5, gives already the idea that the limit of detection for ammonium needs to be more sensitive during summer time which indicates that the temperature and the pH of the wastewater (seasonal) could have had an influence on the composition as well. Nitrate usually in low levels present in wastewater (<1.14 mg/L) reached significant higher levels in the end of June/July and in the middle of July/August (4.69 - 34.37 mg/L). Besides the significant concentration increase for nitrate (5x) when comparing the 26th of June to the 19th of June, also the typical water ion calcium (3x) was determined in higher levels after the 26th of June. This phenomena could be closely related to the extensive use of fireworks (New Year's Eve Effect) before and during the San Juan celebrations at the 24th of June in Spain, but needs to be proven with more continuous data and instruments with a higher sensitivity (e.g. ICP-MS) and selectivity (e. g. electrodes, sensors, SI-CE-C⁴D).

Table 7: Anion and cation concentrations determined in wastewater from the WWTP of Girona, a city in the north of Spain with 100,266 inhabitants as of 2018 (mg/L).

Date	Nitrate	Phosphate	Sulfate	Potassium	Ammonium
15 May	0.54	1.98	25.09	35.23	48.90
20 May	0.67	N/A	N/A	13.46	32.21
27 May	1.14	N/A	23.31	27.79	0.61
19 June	4.69	4.56	N/A	31.60	2.09
26 June	23.26	1.04	18.84	22.89	1.88
01 July	19.03	1.64	21.18	26.37	1.80
09 July	2.76	5.87	19.71	25.00	<LOQ
15 July	20.14	1.92	18.11	N/A	<LOQ
22 July	21.36	5.77	21.95	N/A	<LOQ
29 July	27.77	7.44	18.16	N/A	<LOQ
05 Aug	34.37	8.25	17.74	27.18	<LOQ
12 Aug	0.00	9.70	15.98	26.18	47.28
12 Aug	0.07	6.69	8.18	28.04	38.40
21 Aug	N/A	10.55	15.01	30.24	41.74
25 Aug	0.02	9.10	2.11	28.25	57.05
26 Aug	0.01	10.19	1.37	34.86	59.87
27 Aug	0.02	9.48	1.41	33.32	57.14

N/A = not determined, <LOQ = under limit of quantification, Aug = August.

Figure 5: Plot of the selected ions, related to explosives, in wastewater from the WWTP of Girona.

The data provided from both WWTPs foreshadows what background concentrations of ions can be expected in wastewater and to which extent the ionic composition of wastewater can change due to seasonal influences, celebrations with explosive/fireworks (NYE), human behaviour or other influences (Restrictions, Regulations, Laws).

Spatial Differences and Temporal Changes

A case study in 2013 determined perchlorate concentration in water, snow, soil and corn in North-eastern China investigated seasonal and other influencing factors.⁵⁹ The work showed that there are major differences in perchlorate concentration in soil samples, when comparing samples from rural areas (3.38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) to samples from downtown (5.90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$). The authors suspected that those spatial differences could have been caused by fireworks used to celebrate Chinese New Year (approx. 1-2 month before sampling), because there is more fireworks released in a city than in rural areas. The 2013 study also showed that temporal changes can occur as a consequence of seasons and NYE. Comparing samples from September (summer) and March (spring), there was almost no sample containing perchlorate in September to samples from March containing on average 3.87 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ perchlorate, depending on the sampling site (Figure 6, d). Figure 6 (b, c) are showing an increase of perchlorate concentration in the two examined rivers (A-shi and Songhua river in Harbin, China). The concentration of perchlorate increased, the closer to sampling site was located to the downtown area (Figure 6, a). Also, the levels of perchlorate increased in both rivers, the closer they were to their connection. The range of detection in which concentration changes of perchlorate occur in water is $<0.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, that could be a good indication for what we might expect in wastewater.

Figure 6: Spatial differences and temporal changes of perchlorate investigated in Harbin and its surrounding region in North-eastern China. (a) Sampling sites; perchlorate concentrations in (b) the A-shi River, (c) Songhua River and (d) in soil samples. Reprinted from Publication: Seasonal variation and factors influencing perchlorate in water, snow, soil and corns in North-eastern China, *Chemosphere* 90(10), Ye, L. et al., 2493–2498, Copyright (2013), with permission from Elsevier.

Cao et al. reviewed on gaseous atmospheric pollutants released from fireworks during big festive celebrations (mostly China, India and EU) and their concentration changes in the air.¹⁶ The work examined not only the concentration changes of gaseous species regarding weather influences like wind, temperature and humidity (temporal, seasonal) but also the relations of spatial differences (national-level, provincial-level). Additionally the concentrations of soluble target ions in those particles emitted were reviewed and potassium and sulfate had increased the most significant

during celebrations in China and India. Differences in ion patterns of cities could be related to the differences in regulations of components in each country, to the preference of the people doing pyrotechnics or to the selection of the ions determined during those studies. If we assume that those ions/particles released are also able to reach the sewage we should get an idea of what ions increasing during firework use at NYE in the sewer system.

Responsible for natural ion concentration changes in wastewater/sewage is storm water (heavy rain or snow storms) which will dilute and ‘pollute’ the wastewater/sewage. Normally precipitation soaks into the ground, but urban areas are covered in buildings, parking lots, roads and other hard surfaces that cannot absorb the water and flows over the hard surfaces directly into the sewer system and can therefore contain nitrogen and phosphorus originating from fertilizers, pet and yard waste⁶⁰ but also explosives residues from celebrations. It needs more empirical data to determine and investigate what are acute (peak) and what are long term influences on the composition of the sewage. Not only the weather but also the sewer system structure, human activity like traffic, water consumption and population density (inhabitants/m³) will therefore have the biggest influence on the dilution and pollution.

Comparison and Summary of the Findings

In the case of IEDs the literature points to chlorate, perchlorate, nitrate and azide as tracer ions (Table 8, blue), whereas for consumer fireworks potassium, aluminium, magnesium, perchlorate and nitrate are highlighted as tracer ions (Table 8, green). Mostly monitored and reported inorganic ions in wastewater/sewage are *ortho*-phosphate, nitrite, nitrate, ammonium, sulfate, chloride and several metals. The findings summarized in Table 9 show the range of the concentrations we can expect for inorganic ions related to explosives in wastewater. This findings will also contribute valid information to the future selection of ions for monitoring, the establishment of a background levels and the evaluation of significant changes due to natural (seasons) or man-made (lifestyle) influences such as the evaluation of the NYEE applications.

Table 8: Inorganic ions related to explosives/fireworks compared to inorganic ions present in wastewater.

Cations		Anions		Cations		Anions	
explosives/fireworks				wastewater/sewage			
Na ⁺	Cu ²⁺	ClO ₃ ⁻	IO ₃ ⁻	Na ⁺	Cu ²⁺	ClO ₃ ⁻	
K ⁺	Sr ²⁺	ClO ₂ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	K ⁺		*ClO ₂ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻
NH ₄ ⁺	Ba ²⁺	Cl ⁻	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	NH ₄ ⁺		Cl ⁻	
Mg ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	ClO ₄ ⁻	BrO ₃ ⁻	Mg ²⁺	Cd ²⁺		
Ca ²⁺	Co ²⁺	N ₃ ⁻	Br ⁻	Ca ²⁺			Br ⁻
Mn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	OCN ⁻	Mn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	
Zn ²⁺	Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	NO ₂ ⁻	SCN ⁻	Zn ²⁺		NO ₂ ⁻	
Pb ²⁺	Al ³⁺	PO ₄ ³⁻	CrO ₄ ²⁻	Pb ²⁺		PO ₄ ³⁻	
Cr ³⁺	As ³⁺	I ⁻	F ⁻	Cr ³⁺	As ³⁺		F ⁻
	Cs ⁺						

*<LOQ. Tracer ions for IEDs (blue), consumer firework (green).

Table 9: Summary of the findings regarding presence and expected concentration of ions in wastewater.

Group	Ions	Range
Heavy metals	Hg ₂ ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , As ³⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	0.1 - 217 µg/L
Cations	K ⁺ , Na ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺	5.0 - 200 mg/L
Anions	PO ₄ ³⁻ , Cl ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻	
Anions (explosive related)	F ⁻ , Br ⁻ , ClO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻	0.0 - 1.6 mg/L

Conclusions

Not only will the decision which ions should be monitored be important for method development, also the need for sensitivity when it comes to portability and automation. Real-time monitoring devices working stable over a certain period of time (hours, days) are required for those future on-site measurements. Methods and even prototypes exist but need to be reviewed more detailed, adjusted and tested in the real environment, on-site in the sewer. Being able to determine minor changes of the concentrations of each ion of interest or pattern of those ions related to explosives to such an extent that it becomes possible to narrow down the search area for illegal IED or fireworks manufacturing sites, could be of high value for police investigations, intelligence departments and homeland security. As an example we focused in this review on the NYEE by using wastewater composition data from around NYE and San Juan, to help to confirm the effect on different days. With all the challenges and limitations reviewed to allow the establishment of something like a 'fingerprint' of explosives in sewage, a case study with samples taken from tactical relevant locations in the sewer system during NYE (Amsterdam), or presumably during San Juan (Girona), will give the opportunity to measure and collect statistical data over a longer continuous timespan with higher accuracy. So we can determine trends (seasonal), draw conclusions (regulations of explosives) and validate (background) the identification of explosive traces in the sewer system. Mostly monitored, assessed and reported inorganic ions in wastewater/sewage are *ortho*-phosphate (PO₄³⁻), nitrite (NO₂⁻), nitrate (NO₃⁻), ammonium (NH₄⁺), sulfate (SO₄²⁻), chloride (Cl⁻) and several metals. Heavy metal ions (Hg₂²⁺, Cd²⁺, As³⁺, Ag⁺, Cr³⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺) are present in wastewater in levels of 0.1 - 217 µg/L. The data provided from Spain showed that of all measured species cations (K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺), *ortho*-phosphate (PO₄³⁻), chloride (Cl⁻) and sulfate (SO₄²⁻) varied between 5 - 200 mg/L throughout the year. The concentrations of other explosive related anions (F⁻, Br⁻, ClO₃⁻, ClO₂⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻) in wastewater was between 0.014 - 1.6 mg/L, including some data points that have been under the limit of quantification (LOQ). All measured cations (NH₄⁺, K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) and a few anions (PO₄³⁻, Cl⁻) had significantly (100 - 900%) elevated concentrations in wastewater days after New Year's Eve (31st December) compared to days before. The data also included the analysis of ions in wastewater days before and after San Juan (24th June), with a significant increase of calcium (Ca²⁺) and nitrite (NO₂⁻). To evaluate the New Year's Eve Effect in wastewater we need to monitor carefully selected target ions before, during and after celebrations with fireworks in sewage/wastewater. Since 1998, all sewer systems in the Netherlands have been connected to a treatment plant (CLO), what would make coordinated blanket coverage measurements in the sewer system from an infrastructure point of view easily possible. Due to the sensitivity of the available equipment (SI-CE-C⁴D, ICP-MS) even small changes could be detectable and certain pattern of concentration changes of ions in wastewater/sewage will lead to a better and more precise selection of target ions, consequently to the a better evaluation of the NYEE and presumably to illegal fireworks/IED manufacturing sites.

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Search Strategy - Provided Articles from Supervisor

Suspect screening and quantification of trace organic explosives in wastewater using solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography-high resolution accurate mass spectrometry, Helena Rapp-Wright et al.

The first comprehensive assessment of 34 solid phase extraction sorbents is presented for organic explosive residues in wastewater prior to analysis with liquid chromatography-high resolution accurate mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). A total of 18 explosives were selected including nitramines, nitrate esters, nitroaromatics and organic peroxides. Three polymeric divinylbenzene-based sorbents were found to be most suitable and one co-polymerised with n-vinyl pyrrolidone offered satisfactory recoveries for 14 compounds in fortified wastewater (77–124%). Limits of detection in matrix ranged from 0.026–23 g L⁻¹ with R² ≥ 0.98 for most compounds. The method was applied to eight 24-h composite wastewater samples from a London wastewater works and one compound, 2,4-dinitrotoluene, was determined over five days between 332 and 468 g day⁻¹ (225–303 ng L⁻¹). To further exploit the suspect screening capability, 17 additional explosives, precursors and transformation products were screened in spiked wastewater samples. Of these, 14 were detected with recoveries from 62 to 92%, highlighting the broad applicability of the method. To our knowledge, this represents the first screen of explosives-related compounds in wastewater from a major European city. This method also allows post-analysis detection of new or emerging compounds using full-scan HRMS datasets to potentially identify and locate illegal manufacture of explosives via wastewater analysis.

Keywords: Sample preparation, Micro-pollutants, Sewage epidemiology, Energetic materials 2,4-dinitrotoluene

Review on physicochemical properties of pollutants released from fireworks: environmental and health effects and prevention, Xinyuan Cao et al.

The pollutants released from fireworks may seriously deteriorate air quality and adversely impact human health. To aid in obtaining comprehensive observations and in establishing effective legislation aimed at controlling the short-term effects of fireworks, we systematically reviewed the findings of previous studies of the impact of fireworks. These studies, primarily located in Asia (>70% studies), Europe, and North America considered particle concentrations, size distribution, morphology, noise, and chemical composition (including water-soluble ions, elements, carbonaceous material, organic matter, and trace gases), along with the associated human health effects during a fireworks display. Forty-one percent of the studies suggested that the concentrations of firework particles were reported to be 1–5 times higher than the respective background values, and the mean ratios PM₁₀/TSP, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀, and PM_{1.0}/PM_{2.5} were 0.64, 0.72, and 0.65, respectively. During festivals, the concentrations of SO₄²⁻ and K⁺ were the highest of the water-soluble ions with the highest concentrations of K and S for major elements and CO and SO₂ for gaseous pollutants. The health effects of particles and gaseous pollutants, including metals,

emitted from fireworks need further epidemiological study to aid in the prevention of health problems and for the treatment of patients. Fireworks industries should use technical innovation to reduce pollutant emissions. Emissions inventories of fireworks displays should be compiled and used in Eulerian models to forecast the spatiotemporal distribution of pollutants and to further assist the government in establishing appropriate restriction levels and legislations that balance environmental protection with the festive spirit.

Keywords: fireworks, atmospheric pollutants, physicochemical characteristics, environmental effects, management and prevention

Use of experimental design in the investigation of stir bar sorptive extraction followed by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry for the analysis of explosives in water samples, Sébastien Schramm et al.

A method for the sensitive quantification of trace amounts of organic explosives in water samples was developed by using stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) followed by liquid desorption and ultra-high performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC–MS/MS). The proposed method was developed and optimized using a statistical design of experiment approach. Use of experimental designs allowed a complete study of 10 factors and 8 analytes including nitro-aromatics, amino-nitro-aromatics and nitric esters. The liquid desorption study was performed using a full factorial experimental design followed by a kinetic study. Four different variables were tested here: the liquid desorption mode (stirring or sonication), the chemical nature of the stir bar (PDMS or PDMS-PEG), the composition of the liquid desorption phase and finally, the volume of solvent used for the liquid desorption. On the other hand, the SBSE extraction study was performed using a Doehlert design. SBSE extraction conditions such as extraction time profiles, sample volume, modifier addition, and acetic acid addition were examined. After optimization of the experimental parameters, sensitivity was improved by a factor 5–30, depending on the compound studied, due to the enrichment factors reached using the SBSE method. Limits of detection were in the ng/L level for all analytes studied. Reproducibility of the extraction with different stir bars was close to the reproducibility of the analytical method (RSD between 4 and 16%). Extractions in various water sample matrices (spring, mineral and underground water) have shown similar enrichment compared to ultrapure water, revealing very low matrix effects. ©

Keywords: Explosives, SBSE, LC–MS, Experimental design, Environment, Aqueous samples

Analytical techniques for the analysis of consumer fireworks, Carlos Martín-Alberca et al.

This review provides an overview of common consumer fireworks, their usual chemical compositions, and some important classification and legal regulations in Western countries. We show the main analytical techniques and methodologies used to determine consumer fireworks. Most articles published to date focused on studying characteristics and properties of pyrotechnic reagents and explosive compositions by thermal techniques. However, a few research papers

focused on the determination of chemical reagents from intact devices or their residues. In this review, we critically review colorimetric tests, and microscopy, spectroscopy, separation and potentiometric techniques. This information is useful for police laboratories in order to identify the consumer fireworks involved in certain incidents.

Keywords: Chemical composition, Colorimetric test, Consumer firework, Explosive, Forensic analysis, Microscopy, Potentiometry, Pyrotechnics, Separation, Spectroscopy

Detection of trace peroxide explosives in environmental samples using solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography mass spectrometry, Sally C. Gamble

This article presents solid phase extraction (SPE) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LCMS) methods for the trace detection of the peroxide explosives triacetone triperoxide (TATP) and hexamethylene triperoxide diamine (HMTD). Furthermore, experimental studies use these methods to explore the efficiency of wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) processes at removing trace levels of peroxide explosives from water samples to assess the application of the developed methods for the detection of explosives in the environment. The principal results of this study showed that the greatest removal of TATP and HMTD from spiked water samples occurred following the biological treatment stage, however, the WWTP processing did not completely remove all of the analytes from the water, suggesting that such chemicals could contaminate downstream river water samples. The toxicity of chemical pollutants is often determined by their concentration, however, even at trace levels, the monitoring of explosives in the natural environment could be extremely informative for the detection of criminal activity as well as long-term effects upon aquatic life. These findings also have significant implications for crime prevention and disruption approaches that can use this type of data as intelligence to guide investigations regarding the source and attribution of detected explosives.

KEYWORDS: Peroxide; explosives; wastewater; removal; intelligence; forensic

Search Strategy - Google Scholar/Science Direct 1

Keywords used for search: Inorganic explosives; Wastewater; Sewage; Chemical analysis; Analytical techniques;

Separation of Small-Mass Ions, Laurel Jones et al.

Traditionally, ion chromatography has been the most powerful method associated with the analysis of small-mass ions. Capillary electrophoresis was first demonstrated as an appropriate technique for the analysis of inorganic species in 1990. Since then, issues with reproducibility and sensitivity have been addressed, and the technique has become complementary as opposed to competitive, primarily due to differences in selectivity between the two approaches. Together, they are useful to the analytical chemist in solving most issues involving the determination of small-mass ions. This includes analysis of metal ions, forensic analyses such as determination of explosives and illicit drug samples, and environmental monitoring.

Keywords: Ion chromatography, Anions, Cations, Simultaneous analysis, Forensic analysis, Metal ions, Environmental monitoring

Electrochemical Sensor for Explosives Precursors' Detection in Water, Cloé Desmet et al.

Although all countries are intensifying their efforts against terrorism and increasing their mutual cooperation, terrorist bombing is still one of the greatest threats to society. The discovery of hidden bomb factories is of primary importance in the prevention of terrorism activities. Criminals preparing improvised explosives (IE) use chemical substances called precursors. These compounds are released in the air and in the waste water during IE production. Tracking sources of precursors by analyzing air or wastewater can then be an important clue for bomb factories' localization. We are reporting here a new multiplex electrochemical sensor dedicated to the on-site simultaneous detection of three explosive precursors, potentially used for improvised explosive device preparation (hereafter referenced as B01, B08, and B15, for security disclosure reasons and to avoid being detrimental to the security of the counter-explosive EU action). The electrochemical sensors were designed to be disposable and to combine ease of use and portability in a screen-printed eight-electrochemical cell array format. The working electrodes were modified with different electrodeposited metals: gold, palladium, and platinum. These different coatings giving selectivity to the multi-sensor through a "fingerprint"-like signal subsequently analyzed using partial least squares-discriminant analysis (PLS-DA). Results are given regarding the detection of the three compounds in a real environment and in the presence of potentially interfering species.

Keywords: bomb factory; electrochemical array; explosive precursors; improvised explosives; partial least squares-discriminant analysis

Ion Chromatography as a Reference Method for Determination of Inorganic Ions in Water and Wastewater, Rajmund Michalski

Water analysis is an important part of the chemical analysis of environmental samples. The development of new methods of water analysis and improvement of existing ones is a major task for analytical chemists. Analysis of common inorganic anions and cations in water is mandatory. Ion chromatography has almost replaced most of the wet chemical methods used in water analysis. The demands from regulators for justifiable analytical results and from laboratories for validated methods have led to necessity to standardize ion chromatography methods. The paper is a review of application of ion chromatography for the determination of inorganic anions (F^- , Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , BrO_3^- , ClO_2^- , ClO_3^- , PO_3^{4-} , SO_2^{3-} , SO_2^{4-} , CrO_2^{4-} , I^- , SCN^- , and $S_2O_2^{3-}$) and cations (Li^+ , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , K^+ , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+}) in water and wastewater.

Keywords ion chromatography, water analysis, anions, cations

Applications of Ion Chromatography for the Determination of Inorganic Cations, R. Michalski

Ion chromatography is an analytical technique that has revolutionized analysis of inorganic and organic ions, and has changed analytical chemistry in dramatic ways during the past 30 years. Due to a strong environmental impact, metal ion determination and speciation have received significant attention in the last years. Acceptance of ion chromatography for anion analysis was very rapid, primarily because of lack of alternative methods that could quickly and accurately determine anions in a single analysis. However, the situation regarding the analysis of cations was quite different, as there are many fast and sensitive spectroscopic methods, as well as polarography and stripping voltammetry. This paper is a review of application of ion chromatography for the determination of inorganic cations of alkali, alkaline earth, ammonia, heavy and transition metals as well as lanthanides and actinides in environmental samples.

Keywords: Ion chromatography, alkali and alkaline earth metals, heavy metals, transition metals, lanthanides, actinides

Forensic Identification of Inorganic Explosives by Ion Chromatography, Greg W. Dicoski et al.

While there is a great deal of published literature describing methods for the analysis of organic explosives by various methods, there are comparatively few publications concerning the analysis of explosives based on inorganic chemicals. This mini-review examines the literature that is concerned with the analysis of such explosives, commonly referred to as improvised explosive devices, using ion chromatography. Pertinent details from the reviewed publications are used to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of these methods and several comparisons are also made to other analytical techniques. The general utility and limitations of the reported research for the analysis of improvised explosive devices are discussed and future directions are proposed.

Keywords: Ion chromatography, explosives, forensic analysis, improvised explosive devices, anion, cation

Ion chromatography-mass spectrometry: A review of recent technologies and applications in forensic and environmental explosives analysis, Leon Barron et al.

The development and application of ion chromatography (IC) coupled to mass spectrometry (MS) is discussed herein for the quantitative determination of low-order explosives-related ionic species in environmental and forensic sample types. Issues relating to environmental explosives contamination and the need for more confirmatory IC-MS based applications in forensic science are examined. In particular, the compatibility of a range of IC separation modes with MS detection is summarised along with the analytical challenges that have been overcome to facilitate determinations at the ng- $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ level. Observed trends in coupling IC to inductively coupled plasma and electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry form a particular focus. This review also includes a discussion of the relative performance of reported IC-MS methods in comparison to orthogonal ion separation-based, spectrometric and spectroscopic approaches to confirmatory detection of low-order explosives. Finally, some promising areas for future research are highlighted and discussed with respect to potential IC-MS applications.

Keywords: Ion chromatography, Mass spectrometry, Oxyhalides, Cations, Anions, Explosives

Capillary electrophoresis for continuous nitrogen quantification in wastewater treatment processes, Roland Fuiko

A water quality analyzer based on the working principle of capillary electrophoresis (CE) was developed to determine ionic inorganic nitrogen compounds contained in wastewater samples. The instrument provides simultaneous quantification of anions and cations by superimposing hydrodynamic pumping with electrokinetic motion. It features a single separation capillary with contactless conductivity detection and a sequential injection manifold for fluid handling. Dynamic adaption of the system calibration was enabled by the use of a high precision pressure regulator to cover a wide measurement range showing low relative standard deviations (< 2 %) and high measurement accuracy comparable to conventional wastewater analyzers. The prototype is transportable, integrated in a 19 in. rack and connected to a membrane filter system developed for direct sample aspiration in the wastewater process. For operation on site, only a power supply and a network connection for remote control is necessary. Continuous operation was demonstrated over 24 h at the aeration tank of a pilot scale wastewater treatment plant at TU Wien and a good correlation with laboratory results was achieved. At this time, there is no device available, on the market, to analyze all nitrogen species in one assembly with limited hardware complexity and chemical demand. This entails a significant step forward towards automated water quality monitoring with respect to the implementation of new advanced wastewater treatment technologies.

Keywords: Automated on-line monitoring, Wastewater treatment, Simultaneous anion/cation detection, Nitrogen quantification, Capillary electrophoresis, Anammox

Multiparametric automated system for sulfate, nitrite and nitrate monitoring in drinking water and wastewater based on sequential injection analysis, A. Ayala et al.

An automated monitoring system for sulfate, nitrite and nitrate based on sequential injection analysis (SIA) was developed. For nitrite determination the modified Griess-Ilosvay method was used, whereas nitrate was previously reduced to nitrite using a cadmium column followed by nitrite determination. A turbidimetric method was carried out in order to determine sulfate. The results showed that the proposed SIA monitoring system constitutes an effective approach for nitrite, nitrate and sulfate determination since it is able to determine levels required by international agencies that regulate these parameters in water. Detection limits of 0.0207 mg N L⁻¹, 0.0022 mg N L⁻¹ and 3 mg SO₄²⁻ L⁻¹ were obtained for nitrate, nitrite and sulfate, respectively. The developed method offers also typical characteristics of the multi commutated systems, as portability, low reagents consumption and the subsequently minimization of waste generation. The proposed system was successfully applied to drinking water and wastewater samples and validated with a certified river water sample (ION-96.3, LGC Standards).

Keywords: Sulfate, Nitrite, Nitrate, Sequential injection analysis, Multiparametric monitor, Drinking water, Wastewater

Recent advances in capillary electrophoresis instrumentation for the analysis of explosives, Matías Calcerrada et al.

Capillary electrophoresis (CE) is a well-established analytical separation technique. Owing to its high versatility, major advancements have been made with regard to the instrumental set-ups during the last years. New strategies have been proposed to develop high-sensitive methods, portable CE or miniaturized devices. These techniques are of great interest in the analysis of explosives, which generally requires a highly selective approach. This review provides a recent perspective (from the beginning of 2008 to March 2015) on the use of CE for the analysis of explosives. First, a general description of explosives is made, emphasizing the role of separation techniques and specifically CE. Next, the most recent works focused on the analysis of explosives by using conventional CE, portable CE and microchip CE are compared and critically discussed. Besides, other emerging techniques for the analysis of explosives are referred and compared to CE results. Finally, future perspectives for the analysis of explosives by CE are proposed.

Keywords: Capillary electrophoresis Explosive Inorganic Instrumentation Microchip Organic Portable CE Recent CE Review Sensor

Search Strategy - Google Scholar/ScienceDirect 2

Keywords used for search: Inorganic explosives; Wastewater; Sewage; analysis; sampling; explosive traces; post-blast; pre-blast; aqueous samples; environmental samples; explosive traces and several ions/elements from the list

Reviewed book section: Determination of Trace Metals in Waste Water and Their Removal Processes, Asli Baysal et al.

Paragraph from conclusion:

The analysis of wastewater for trace and heavy metal contamination is an important step in ensuring human and environmental health. Wastewater is regulated differently in different countries, but the goal is to minimize the pollution introduced into natural waterways. In recent years, metal production emissions have decreased in many countries due to legislation, improved cleaning technology and altered industrial activities. Today and in the future, dis- sipate losses from consumption of various metal containing goods are of most concern. Therefore, wastewater may need to be measured for a variety of metals at different concentrations, in different wastewater matrices. A variety of inorganic techniques can be used to measure trace elements in wastewater including atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) and ICP mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Depending upon the number of elements that need to be determined and the number of samples that need to be run, the most suitable technique for business requirements can be chosen.

Sequential injection system with multi-parameter analysis capability for water quality measurement, Natcha Kaewwonglom et al.

A simple sequential injection (SI) system with capability to determine multi-parameter has been developed for the determination of iron, manganese, phosphate and ammonium. A simple and compact colorimeter was fabricated in the laboratory to be employed as a detector. The system was optimized for suitable conditions for determining each parameter by changing software program and without reconfiguration of the hardware. Under the optimum conditions, the methods showed linear ranges of 0.2-10 mg L⁻¹ for iron and manganese determinations, and 0.3-5.0 mg L⁻¹ for phosphate and ammonium determinations, with correlation coefficients of 0.9998, 0.9973, 0.9987 and 0.9983, respectively. The system provided detection limits of 0.01, 0.14, 0.004 and 0.02 mg L⁻¹ for iron, manganese, phosphate and ammonium, respectively. The proposed system has good precision, low chemical consumption and high throughput. It was applied for monitoring water quality of Ping river in Chiang Mai, Thailand. Recoveries of the analysis were obtained in the range of 82-119%.

Keywords: Sequential injection analysis, Multi-parameter, Water quality, Iron, Manganese, Ammonium, Phosphate, Ping river

Search Strategy - Google Scholar/Science Direct 3

Keywords: used for search: Identification, analysis, inorganic, improved, explosives, residues, detection, no wastewater, fireworks, pyrotechnic, pre-blast, post-blast

Identification of inorganic ions in post-blast explosive residues using portable CE instrumentation and capacitively coupled contactless conductivity detection, Hutchinson J.P. et al.

Novel CE methods have been developed on portable instrumentation adapted to accommodate a capacitively coupled contactless conductivity detector for the separation and sensitive detection of inorganic anions and cations in post-blast explosive residues from homemade inorganic explosive devices. The methods presented combine sensitivity and speed of analysis for the wide range of inorganic ions used in this study. Separate methods were employed for the separation of anions and cations. The anion separation method utilised a low conductivity 70mM Tris/70mM CHES aqueous electrolyte (pH 8.6) with a 90 cm capillary coated with hexadimethrine bromide to reverse the EOF. Fifteen anions could be baseline separated in 7 min with detection limits in the range 27–240 mg/L. A selection of ten anions deemed most important in this application could be separated in 45 s on a shorter capillary (30.6 cm) using the same electrolyte. The cation separation method was performed on a 73 cm length of fused-silica capillary using an electrolyte system composed of 10mM histidine and 50mM acetic acid, at pH 4.2. The addition of the complexants, 1mM hydroxyisobutyric acid and 0.7mM 18-crown-6 ether, enhanced selectivity and allowed the separation of eleven inorganic cations in under 7 min with detection limits in the range 31–240 mg/L. The developed methods were successfully field tested on post-blast residues obtained from the controlled detonation of homemade explosive devices. Results were verified using ion chromatographic analyses of the same samples.

Keywords: Contactless conductivity detection / Homemade explosive devices / Inorganic anions and cations / Portable CE / Post-blast residues

Identification of Inorganic Improvised Explosive Devices by Analysis of Postblast Residues Using Portable Capillary Electrophoresis Instrumentation and Indirect Photometric Detection with a Light-Emitting Diode, Joseph P. Hutchinson et al.

A commercial portable capillary electrophoresis (CE) instrument has been used to separate inorganic anions and cations found in post-blast residues from improvised explosive devices (IEDs) of the type used frequently in terrorism attacks. The purpose of this analysis was to identify the type of explosive used. The CE instrument was modified for use with an in-house miniaturized light emitting diode (LED) detector to enable sensitive indirect photometric detection to be employed for

the detection of 15 anions (acetate, benzoate, carbonate, chlorate, chloride, chlorite, cyanate, fluoride, nitrate, nitrite, perchlorate, phosphate, sulfate, thiocyanate, thiosulfate) and 12 cations (ammonium, monomethylammonium, ethylammonium, potassium, sodium, barium, strontium, magnesium, manganese, calcium, zinc, lead) as the target analytes. These ions are known to be present in postblast residues from inorganic IEDs constructed from ammonium nitrate/fuel oil mixtures, black powder, and chlorate/perchlorate/sugar mixtures. For the analysis of cations, a blue LED (470 nm) was used in conjunction with the highly absorbing cationic dye, chrysoidine (absorption maximum at 453 nm). A nonaqueous background electrolyte comprising 10 mM chrysoidine in methanol was found to give greatly improved baseline stability in comparison to aqueous electrolytes due to the increased solubility of chrysoidine and its decreased adsorption onto the capillary wall. Glacial acetic acid (0.7% v/v) was added to ensure chrysoidine was protonated and to enhance separation selectivity by means of complexation with transition metal ions. The 12 target cations were separated in less than 9.5 min with detection limits of 0.11-2.30 mg/L (calculated at a signal-to-noise ratio of 3). The anions separation system utilized a UV LED (370 nm) in conjunction with an aqueous chromate electrolyte (absorption maximum at 371 nm) consisting of 10 mM chromium(VI) oxide and 10 mM sodium chromate, buffered with 40 mM tris(hydroxymethyl)-aminomethane at pH 8.05. All 15 target anions were baseline separated in less than 9 min with limits of detection ranging from 0.24 to 1.15 mg/L (calculated at a signal-to-noise ratio of 3). Use of the portable instrumentation in the field was demonstrated by analyzing postblast residues in a mobile laboratory immediately after detonation of the explosive devices. Profiling the ionic composition of the inorganic IEDs allowed identification of the chemicals used in their construction.

Identification of homemade inorganic explosives by ion chromatographic analysis of post-blast residues, Cameron Johns et al.

Anions and cations of interest for the post-blast identification of homemade inorganic explosives were separated and detected by ion chromatographic (IC) methods. The ionic analytes used for identification of explosives in this study comprised 18 anions (acetate, benzoate, bromate, carbonate, chlorate, chloride, chlorite, chromate, cyanate, fluoride, formate, nitrate, nitrite, perchlorate, phosphate, sulfate, thiocyanate and thiosulfate) and 12 cations (ammonium, barium(II), calcium(II), chromium(III), ethylammonium, magnesium(II), manganese(II), methylammonium, potassium(I), sodium(I), strontium(II), and zinc(II)). Two IC separations are presented, using suppressed IC on a Dionex AS20 column with potassium hydroxide as eluent for anions, and non-suppressed IC for cations using a Dionex SCS 1 column with oxalic acid/acetonitrile as eluent. Conductivity detection was used in both cases. Detection limits for anions were in the range 2–27.4 ppb, and for cations were in the range 13–115 ppb. These methods allowed the explosive residue ions to be identified and separated from background ions likely to be present in the environment. Linearity (over a calibration range of 0.05–50 ppm) was evaluated for both methods, with r^2 values ranging from 0.9889 to 1.000. Reproducibility over 10 consecutive injections of a 5 ppm standard ranged from 0.01 to 0.22% relative standard deviation (RSD) for retention time and 0.29 to 2.16% RSD for peak area. The anion and cation separations were

performed simultaneously by using two Dionex ICS-2000 chromatographs served by a single autoinjector. The efficacy of the developed methods was demonstrated by analysis of residue samples taken from witness plates and soils collected following the controlled detonation of a series of different inorganic homemade explosives. The results obtained were also confirmed by parallel analysis of the same samples by capillary electrophoresis (CE) with excellent agreement being obtained.

Keywords: Ion chromatography, Cations, Anions, Homemade inorganic explosives, Counter-terrorism

Identification of inorganic improvised explosive devices using sequential injection capillary electrophoresis and contactless conductivity detection, Blanco GA et al.

A simple sequential injection capillary electrophoresis (SI-CE) instrument with capacitively coupled contactless conductivity detection (C(4)D) has been developed for the rapid separation of anions relevant to the identification of inorganic improvised explosive devices (IEDs). Four of the most common explosive tracer ions, nitrate, perchlorate, chlorate, and azide, and the most common background ions, chloride, sulfate, thiocyanate, fluoride, phosphate, and carbonate, were chosen for investigation. Using a separation electrolyte comprising 50 mM tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, 50 mM cyclohexyl-2-aminoethanesulfonic acid, pH 8.9 and 0.05% poly(ethyleneimine) (PEI) in a hexadimethrine bromide (HDMB)-coated capillary it was possible to partially separate all 10 ions within 90 s. The combination of two cationic polymer additives (PEI and HDMB) was necessary to achieve adequate selectivity with a sufficiently stable electroosmotic flow (EOF), which was not possible with only one polymer. Careful optimization of variables affecting the speed of separation and injection timing allowed a further reduction of separation time to 55 s while maintaining adequate efficiency and resolution. Software control makes high sample throughput possible (60 samples/h), with very high repeatability of migration times [0.63-2.07% relative standard deviation (RSD) for 240 injections]. The separation speed does not compromise sensitivity, with limits of detection ranging from 23 to 50 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for all the explosive residues considered, which is 10 \times lower than those achieved by indirect absorbance detection and 2 \times lower than those achieved by C(4)D using portable benchtop instrumentation. The combination of automation, high sample throughput, high confidence of peak identification, and low limits of detection makes this methodology ideal for the rapid identification of inorganic IED residues.

Anions in pre- and post-blast consumer fireworks by capillary electrophoresis Carlos Martin-Alberca et al.

Consumer fireworks are a heterogeneous group of pyrotechnic items widely used by citizens around the world. There are a wide number of forensic cases related to consumer fireworks that require knowing their chemical composition and variety of designs to conduct accurate and comprehensive analyses. In this research paper, a selection of six consumer firework types (firecracker, rocket, pyrotechnic fountain, pyrotechnic battery, sparkler, and smoke bomb) is

physically described and their anionic compositions are determined. Pre-blast (fuses and charges) samples and postblast residues of the different consumer fireworks were analyzed by CE in order to determine their anionic composition. Different types of chemical compositions in fuses and pyrotechnic charges were determined, although they were not related to any type of item. Additionally, several discrepancies were found between the analytical results and the declared item compositions. Regarding post-blast residues, a huge variety of anions were identified and attributed to some unconsumed starting materials and different chemical reactions occurring during combustion.

Keywords: Anions / Capillary electrophoresis / Consumer fireworks / Forensic analysis / Pyrotechnics

Composition profile of low explosives from cases in India, Kuila et al.

About 1000 samples of explosives and post-blast residues were analysed using routine analytical procedures. The results were confirmed by ion chromatography and scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive X-ray analyzer (SEM-EDXA) (for a number of samples) for better comprehension of the elements present. Common, easily available compounds like potassium nitrate (KNO₃), potassium chlorate (KClO₃), arsenic sulphide (As₂S₃), sulphur (S), aluminium (Al), etc. were used in varying combinations for the manufacture of improvised low explosives. Composition profiles of the explosives and their origin may be useful in tracing the criminals. Restrictions and proper monitoring of these substances are suggested to reduce explosions causing damage of public and private properties and loss of lives. # 2005 Elsevier Ireland Ltd. All rights reserved.

Keywords: Explosives; Composition profile; Ion chromatography; Pyrotechnic materials; SEM-EDX

The additional literature was found in the references in the literature mentioned above. Additional literature was provided by Frederic Been (KWR) from The Netherlands, Pablo Gago-Ferrero (ICRA) from Spain and Frank Hauser (BKA) from Germany.